

Proof of the 3x+1 problem

Alin Grigoras

Abstract

In this paper, we present a proof of the Collatz conjecture, a longstanding open problem in mathematics. The Collatz conjecture posits that for any positive integer n , applying the iterative process defined by the rules $n \rightarrow \frac{n}{2}$ when n is even and $n \rightarrow 3n + 1$ when n is odd, will eventually lead to the number 1. We approach the problem by introducing the concept of "beta numbers", which are numbers that can be traced back to powers of 2 via a reverse Collatz operation, $R(n) = \frac{n-1}{3}$, when applicable.

Our main result demonstrates that every odd number $d \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ generates a sequence of even numbers, $2^k \times d$, where at least one number in the sequence satisfies $N \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, making it a beta (β); and every odd number $d \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ can be traced back to a power of 2. We then show that each β can be recursively traced back to a power of 2, confirming that every number, through a finite number of steps, leads to the cycle $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$. Furthermore, we establish that no other cycles exist, and the process is finite for all integers.

This result provides a full resolution to the Collatz conjecture by confirming that all numbers eventually reach 1. The proof relies on modular arithmetic, recursion, and properties of powers of 2.

Introduction

The Collatz conjecture, also known as the $3n + 1$ problem, is one of the most famous open problems in mathematics. Despite its apparent simplicity, it has remained unsolved for decades and continues to capture the attention of both professional and amateur mathematicians alike. The conjecture describes a sequence generated from any positive integer n by applying the following iterative process:

- If n is even, divide it by 2, i.e., $n \rightarrow \frac{n}{2}$,

- If n is odd, apply $n \rightarrow 3n + 1$.

The conjecture posits that for any initial value of n , repeated application of this process will eventually reach the number 1, regardless of how large n may be. This process then enters the cycle $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$, repeating indefinitely.

Despite extensive numerical verification, no general proof has been established that covers all positive integers. The conjecture has connections to various areas of mathematics, including number theory, dynamical systems, and computer science.

In this paper, we propose a novel approach to the Collatz conjecture by introducing the concept of "beta numbers". These numbers can be traced back to powers of 2 through the reverse application of the Collatz transformation $R(n) = \frac{n-1}{3}$, under the condition that $n - 1$ is divisible by 3. Our approach shows that every odd number generates a sequence of even numbers, half of which are beta numbers, leading recursively to powers of 2 and the trivial cycle $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$.

The paper is structured as follows: In Preliminaries section, we introduce formal definitions and preliminary results regarding beta numbers. Then we present the main proof, demonstrating how every odd number leads to a beta number and how each beta can be traced back to a power of 2. In Section 5, we establish the finiteness of the process and rule out the existence of non-trivial cycles. Finally, in the last section, we conclude by summarizing our findings and discussing potential future implications.

Preliminaries

In this section, we introduce the key definitions and notations that will be used throughout the paper. We begin by formally defining the Collatz transformation, the concept of beta numbers, and the reverse Collatz operation, which will play a central role in our approach.

1. Collatz Transformation

The Collatz transformation defines a sequence starting from any positive integer n by applying the following rules:

- If n is even, divide it by 2, i.e., $n \rightarrow \frac{n}{2}$,
- If n is odd, apply $n \rightarrow 3n + 1$.

The Collatz conjecture posits that for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$, repeated application of the Collatz transformation will eventually reach the number 1. This transformation can be applied iteratively to generate a sequence:

$$n_0 = n, n_{k+1} = \begin{cases} \frac{n_k}{2}, & \text{if } n_k \text{ is even,} \\ 3n_k + 1, & \text{if } n_k \text{ is odd.} \end{cases}$$

Our goal is to show that every such sequence eventually enters the cycle $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$.

2. Beta Numbers

Definition 1 (Beta Numbers of Degree g):

Consider the sequence of powers of 2: 2^k where $k \geq 0$. This sequence yields numbers of the form $1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64, \dots$, and contains a special subset of numbers called beta numbers of degree zero (denoted β_0), which are directly reducible to 1 through repeated applications of the operation $n \rightarrow \frac{n}{2}$.

Beta numbers are defined by the property that $\frac{\beta-1}{3} \in \mathbb{Z}$, meaning that when subtracting 1 from a beta number and dividing by 3, the result is an integer. Due to the cyclical behavior of powers of 2 modulo 3 (either $1 \pmod 3$ or $2 \pmod 3$), we can assert that beta numbers are uniformly distributed along the sequence of powers of 2.

For any beta number β , applying the inverse Collatz operation $R(\beta) = \frac{\beta-1}{3}$ results in an odd integer d . This odd number d forms the starting point of another sequence of powers of 2 of the form $2^k \times d$, which similarly contains beta numbers. These numbers are called beta numbers of degree one (denoted β_1).

Figure 1: Schema of the β layer, the connections between them and the operations involved.

This pattern continues indefinitely, yielding beta numbers of higher degrees. Specifically, the beta numbers of degree g (β_g) arise from sequences initiated by applying the inverse Collatz operation $\frac{\beta-1}{3}$ to beta numbers of lower degrees.

Thus, we define beta numbers of arbitrary degree recursively:

- A beta number of degree zero (β_0) is any number in the sequence 2^k that satisfies $\frac{\beta-1}{3} \in \mathbb{Z}$.
- A beta number of degree g (β_g) is an even number that is a multiple of an odd number d (where d is obtained via the reverse Collatz operation from a beta number of degree $g-1$), such that $2^k \times d \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.

3. Reverse Collatz Operation

The reverse Collatz operation is the inverse of the standard Collatz transformation applied to odd numbers. It is defined as:

$$R(n) = \frac{n-1}{3},$$

where $n-1$ is divisible by 3. This operation allows us to trace a number back through the Collatz process, provided the number satisfies the condition $N \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.

4. Powers of 2 and Modulo 3 Behavior

Lemma 1:

The powers of 2 modulo 3 follow a cyclical pattern:

$$2^1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}, \quad 2^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \quad 2^3 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}, \quad 2^4 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \dots$$

Thus, the powers of 2 alternate between $2 \pmod{3}$ and $1 \pmod{3}$, forming a cycle with period 2. This periodicity implies the following behavior when multiplying powers of 2 by an arbitrary odd number d , where $d \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$:

- If $d \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, then $2^k \times d \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ for even k and $2^k \times d \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ for odd k .
- If $d \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, then $2^k \times d \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ for even k and $2^k \times d \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ for odd k .

This guarantees that for any odd number $d \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, there exists some k such that $2^k \times d \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. This ensures that the sequence $2^k \times d$ will eventually yield a number congruent to 1 modulo 3.

5. Sequences of Even Numbers Generated by Odd Numbers

Given any odd number d , we can generate a sequence of even numbers by multiplying d by successive powers of 2:

$$N_k = 2^k \times d \quad \text{for } k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

Using Lemma 1, we know that for some k , $N_k \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, which guarantees that N_k is a beta number. This sequence helps trace every odd number back to a beta number, and ultimately, to a power of 2.

5. The case of $D \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$

For the case where $d \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, we apply the following approach.

If d is even, we successively divide d by 2 until an odd number d' is reached. This odd number d' serves as the "head" of the beta layer (the initial element of the layer). Once the odd number d' is obtained, we apply the transformation $3n + 1$ to move to a layer of lower degree.

It is important to note that all layers whose head is divisible by 3 (i.e., $d \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$) do not contain any beta numbers. In the context of the Collatz conjecture, these

layers are "disconnected" from layers of higher degree, but not from layer of lower degree, which lead to 1.

Proof of the Collatz Conjecture

In this section, we provide the proof that every positive integer n , when subjected to the Collatz transformation, eventually reaches the number 1. The proof proceeds by demonstrating that every odd number generates a sequence of even numbers that contains at least one beta number, which can be traced back to a power of 2. We then show that the process of applying the Collatz transformation is finite for every number, and no cycles exist other than the trivial cycle $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$.

Step 1: Every odd number generates a beta number

We start by considering any odd number $d \in \mathbb{N}$. By definition, multiplying d by powers of 2 generates a sequence of even numbers $N_k = 2^k \times d$, $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$. Using Lemma 1 regarding the cyclical behavior of powers of 2 modulo 3:

$$2^1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}, \quad 2^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \quad 2^3 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}, \quad 2^4 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \dots$$

we see that for any odd $d \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, there will always be a k such that:

$$2^k \times d \equiv 1 \pmod{3}.$$

Since $N_k \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, this means that N_k is a beta number and satisfies:

$$\frac{N_k - 1}{3} \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

Therefore, for every odd $d \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, there exists a k such that N_k is a beta number.

If $d \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, we can apply $3n + 1$, which lead to a beta number of a lower degree layer; so also odd numbers $d \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ are connected to a beta number.

This shows that every odd number generates a sequence of even numbers that includes a beta number.

Step 2: Beta numbers can be traced back to a power of 2

Given any beta number β_g , where $\beta_g = 2^k \times d$, we can apply the reverse Collatz operation:

$$R(\beta_g) = \frac{N-1}{3},$$

because $\beta_g \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Applying the operation, we reduce β_g back to a smaller odd number, or in the case of powers of 2, eventually to a beta of degree zero, $\beta_0 = 2^m$, for some m .

Since the reverse Collatz operation is defined whenever $N \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, and beta numbers satisfy this condition, the process of applying $R(N)$ is finite and deterministic. By recursively applying $R(N)$, the number reaches a power of 2:

$$\beta_0 = 2^m.$$

At this point, the number β_0 follows the standard Collatz transformation for powers of 2, which continues to divide by 2 until it reaches the trivial cycle $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$. Every beta number can be traced back to a power of 2, and every power of 2 terminates in the cycle $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$.

Step 3: Beta numbers in sequences

A beta number is defined as any number N that satisfies:

$$\frac{N-1}{3} \in \mathbb{Z},$$

which implies that $N \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. We need to rigorously demonstrate that every sequence of the form $2^k \times d$, where d is an odd number, necessarily contains or is connected at least to one beta number. This is ensured by analyzing the cyclical behavior of powers of 2 modulo 3.

Cyclical Behavior of Powers of 2 Modulo 3

It is well-known that powers of 2 follow a cyclical pattern modulo 3:

$$2^1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}, \quad 2^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \quad 2^3 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}, \quad 2^4 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \dots$$

This shows that powers of 2 alternate between $2 \pmod{3}$ and $1 \pmod{3}$, following a period of 2. This periodicity will be crucial in ensuring that for any odd number $d \not\equiv$

$0 \pmod 3$, the sequence $2^k \times d$ will eventually reach a number congruent to $1 \pmod 3$, i.e., a beta number.

Behavior of $2^k \times d \pmod 3$

Now, let us analyze the sequence $2^k \times d$, where d is any odd number. We want to show that there exists a value of k such that:

$$2^k \times d \equiv 1 \pmod 3.$$

We consider three cases based on the congruence of $d \pmod 3$:

- Case 1: $d \equiv 1 \pmod 3$

If $d \equiv 1 \pmod 3$, the sequence $2^k \times d$ simplifies to:

$$2^k \times d \equiv 2^k \times 1 \pmod 3.$$

Since powers of 2 alternate between $2 \pmod 3$ and $1 \pmod 3$, there will be some k such that $2^k \times d \equiv 1 \pmod 3$, meaning that the sequence will contain a beta number.

- Case 2: $d \equiv 2 \pmod 3$

If $d \equiv 2 \pmod 3$, the sequence $2^k \times d \pmod 3$ becomes:

$$2^k \times d \equiv 2^k \times 2 \pmod 3.$$

Here again, due to the periodicity of powers of 2 modulo 3, the sequence will alternate between $2 \pmod 3$ and $1 \pmod 3$. Therefore, there will exist a value of k such that:

$2^k \times d \equiv 1 \pmod 3$, which means the sequence will contain a beta number.

- Case 3: $d \equiv 0 \pmod 3$

If $d \equiv 0 \pmod 3$, the sequence $2^k \times d \pmod 3$ becomes:

$$2^k \times d \equiv 2^k \times 0 \pmod 3.$$

Here, there will never be a beta number in the series. This kind of layers are not connected to higher beta layers. From this layer, we can go to a lower beta layer, where there certainly will be some beta values since:

$$3 \times d + 1 \not\equiv 0 \pmod 3.$$

Step 4: No non-trivial cycles exist

We now prove that no non-trivial cycles exist in the Collatz sequence. Suppose, for the sake of contradiction, that there exists a non-trivial cycle involving some number $n \neq 1$. Let $n_0, n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k = n_0$ be the numbers in this hypothetical cycle, where n_0 is the smallest number in the cycle.

Case 1: n_0 is even

If n_0 is even, by the Collatz transformation we must apply $n_0 \rightarrow \frac{n_0}{2}$. Since n_0 is the smallest number in the cycle, the transformation $n_0 \rightarrow \frac{n_0}{2}$ produces a smaller number, contradicting the assumption that n_0 is the smallest element of the cycle. Therefore, n_0 cannot be even.

Case 2: n_0 is odd

The demonstration of the non-existence of non-trivial cycles involves examining the structure of layers formed by numbers of the form $2^k \times d$, where d is an odd number (the head of the layer).

For a cycle to exist, the Collatz transformation applied to an odd number d would need to return to the same layer, meaning that $3d + 1$ must be of the form $2^k \times d$ for some integer k . This condition would require solving the equation:

$$3d + 1 = 2^k \times d .$$

Rearranging the equation, we get:

$$3d + 1 = 2^k \times d \Rightarrow d = \frac{1}{2^k - 3} .$$

For d to be an integer, $2^k - 3$ must divide 1, which only happens when $k = 2$. Substituting $k = 2$ into the equation yields $d = 1$.

Thus, the only solution that satisfies the condition $3d + 1 = 2^k \times d$ is $d = 1$, which leads to the trivial cycle $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$. Therefore, no other values of d can form a cycle, ruling out the existence of any non-trivial cycles.

Step 5: Finiteness of the process for all numbers

To prove the finiteness of the Collatz transformation for all numbers, we now show that every number, whether odd or even, eventually reaches 1 in a finite number of steps.

- **Even numbers:** Any even number n is repeatedly divided by 2, and this process will continue until n becomes odd. This is guaranteed because repeated division by 2 always reduces even numbers in a finite number of steps.

- **Odd numbers:** Every odd number d generates a sequence of even numbers $2^k \times d$, as shown in Step 1, and one of these numbers will be a beta number. As demonstrated in Step 2, beta numbers can be traced back to powers of 2, which eventually reach the trivial cycle $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$.

Since the process of reducing odd numbers to beta numbers and powers of 2 is finite, the Collatz transformation must terminate in a finite number of steps for every positive integer $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proof conclusion

We have now shown, in a rigorous manner, that every odd number generates a sequence of even numbers containing a beta number, and that every beta can be recursively traced back to a power of 2. The absence of non-trivial cycles has been established by contradiction, and the finiteness of the process for all numbers is guaranteed by the structure of the Collatz transformation. Therefore, we conclude that the Collatz conjecture is true for all positive integers.

Conclusion

In this paper, we have provided a proof of the Collatz conjecture, which asserts that for any positive integer n , the iterative process defined by the Collatz transformation will eventually lead to the number 1. Our approach introduced the concept of beta numbers, which are even numbers that can be traced back to powers of 2 through the reverse Collatz operation $\frac{n-1}{3}$ when applicable.

We demonstrated that every odd number generates or is connected to a sequence of even numbers $2^k \times d$ that contains at least one beta number. Each beta number can be recursively traced back to a power of 2, ensuring that every number eventually enters the trivial cycle $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$. Furthermore, we established that no non-trivial cycles exist and that the Collatz process is finite for all numbers.

This proof resolves the Collatz conjecture, confirming that the sequence generated by the Collatz transformation always terminates at 1 for all positive integers. The modular arithmetic properties of powers of 2 and the cyclical behavior modulo 3 played a critical role in the structure of the proof.

The resolution of the Collatz conjecture opens up potential avenues for further exploration. While the conjecture has been a standalone problem, the techniques developed here may have applications to other areas of number theory, particularly in the study of iterative processes and dynamical systems. Future research may also

focus on exploring generalized forms of the Collatz conjecture or investigating other iterative systems with similar behavior.